

Assay of some ophthalmic drugs with ammonium meta vanadate reagent

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A simple and convenient method has been developed for the determination of some ophthalmic drugs e.g. Cyclopentolate hydrochloride, Atropine sulphate, Gentamicin sulphate, Tobramycin sulphate, Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride, Norfloxacin, Tropicamide, Naphazoline hydrochloride and Neomycin sulphate in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations. Aliquots (1–5 mg) of the samples are allowed to react with 0.3 N ammonium meta vanadate reagent in acidic medium for required reaction time at boiling water bath. After the reaction is over, the unconsumed reagent is back determined by titration against ferrous ammonium sulphate using *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid indicator. The value of % error, SD and CV prove the method to be precise and reproducible.

A large number of compounds have been used for controlling bacterial activities in different types of diseases. An antimuscarinic agent such as cyclopentolate hydrochloride, Atropine sulphate, and Tropicamide are used as eye drops to cure cycloplegia and mydriasis. Ophthalmic drugs of aminoglycoside group such as Gentamicin sulphate, Tobramycin sulphate and Neomycin sulphate are active against gram-negative bacteria. Fluoroquinolone group of antibacterials e.g. Ciprofloxacin and Norfloxacin are active against gram-positive bacteria. Because of their great medicinal value, their estimations have widely been studied^{1–9}. Most of the above methods involve sophisticated instruments and complicated techniques. In the present paper we describe a simple and convenient method for the determination of above ophthalmic drugs with ammonium meta vanadate reagent.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established after studying the effect of variables such as reaction time, concentration and amount of reagent and sulphuric acid and reaction temperature. Variation in reaction time was found to influence the reaction. It was observed that Naphazoline hydrochloride, Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride, Tropicamide and Neomycin sulphate needs 30 min reaction time, while Gentamicin sulphate, Tobramycin sulphate, Atropine sulphate and Cyclopentolate hydrochloride needs reaction time of 60 min. This variation in reaction time is due to difference in the structure of the compounds. However in case of all the samples a further increase in reaction time does not give any improvement in the results. A lesser reaction time gives higher % error, because of in-

complete reaction. The effect of concentration of reagent was also studied and it was found that the recommended concentration (0.3 N) was suitable for accurate and concordant results. The reaction temperature was the most important factor to be studied. The reactivity of the sample is very slow at ice cool temperature but increases with the rise in temperature and reaches at a maximum level at the temperature of boiling water bath. Direct heating of the reaction mixture on flame or on sand bath was avoided because it gives inconsistent results. The stoichiometric ratio of the reagent with the sample was also established for each compound. Since the present reagents works as strong oxidizing agent it gives different oxidized products depending upon the structure of the compound. Therefore a large variation in the sample to reagent ratio is observed. Results obtained in the present method are accurate and reproducible.

Experimental

Ammonium metavanadate solution (AMV 0.3 N) : 3.5 g of the compound (A.R. grade, Fine-Chem Ltd.) was accurately weighed and dissolved in 5 ml of conc. sulphuric acid in 100 ml volumetric flask and then made up to the mark with distilled water. The solution was standardized against ferrous ammonium sulphate (0.050 N, Merck) using *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid (0.2 g) indicator.

Sample solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) : Accurately weighed (100 mg) sample of pure compounds like Cyclopentolate hydrochloride, Atropine sulphate, Gentamicin sulphate, Tobramycin sulphate, Ciprofloxacin, Tropicamide, Naphazoline hydrochloride and Neomycin sulphate were

dissolved in distilled water in a 100 ml volumetric flask, while Norfloxacin was dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid and then diluted to 100 ml with distilled water. Ophthalmic preparations in the forms of drops were also dissolved similarly.

Procedure : An aliquot containing 1–5 mg of the sample was taken in 100 ml stoppered conical flask and 2 ml of 0.3 N AMV solution and 5 ml of 8 N sulphuric acid for Cyclopentolate, Ciprofloxacin, Norfloxacin and Naphazoline and 5 ml of conc. sulphuric acid for Atropine, Gentamicin,

Tobramycin, Neomycin and Tropicamide was added to it. The reaction mixture was allowed to react at a temperature of boiling water bath for prescribed reaction time. After the reaction was over the contents were cooled to room temperature and unconsumed reagent was determined against ferrous ammonium sulphate using *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid indicator. A blank experiment was also run under identical conditions using all the reagents except the sample. The amount of the sample was calculated by the usual method.

Table 1. Determination of some ophthalmics (pure form) and its pharmaceutical preparations with 0.3 N ammonium meta vanadate reagent

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (ml)	Amount present* (mg)	Reaction time (min)	Molecularity	Amount obtained by calculation** (mg)	Error (%)	SD (mg)	CV (%)
1	Cyclopentolate hydrochloride (pure)	1	0.990	60	6	0.979	-1.07	0.0015	0.1532
		3	2.970			2.947	-0.78	0.0017	0.0577
		5	4.950			4.927	-0.46	0.0022	0.0447
	(a) Cyclopen (D) (optho)	1	0.979			0.970	-0.91	0.0025	0.2577
		3	2.937			2.916	-0.71	0.0028	0.0960
		5	4.895			4.870	-0.52	0.0023	0.0472
	(b) Cyclogyl (D)	1	0.976			0.967	-0.96	0.0021	0.2172
		3	2.928			2.906	-0.74	0.0018	0.0619
		5	4.880			4.854	-0.54	0.0013	0.0268
2	Atropine sulphate (pure)	1	0.987	60	34	0.977	-1.01	0.0035	0.3582
		3	2.961			2.939	-0.74	0.0030	0.1021
		5	4.935			4.912	-0.47	0.0020	0.0407
	(a) (Ophopin) (D) (optho)	1	0.972			0.963	-0.94	0.0023	0.2388
		3	2.916			2.895	-0.71	0.0026	0.0898
		5	4.000			4.836	-0.50	0.0020	0.0414
	(b) Atrisolon (D)	1	0.971			0.961	-1.04	0.0016	0.1665
		3	2.913			2.891	-0.76	0.0012	0.0415
		5	4.855			4.831	-0.49	0.0017	0.0352
3	Gentamicin sulphate (pure)	1	0.986	60	46	0.977	-0.91	0.0014	0.1433
		3	2.958			2.937	-0.72	0.0011	0.0375
		5	4.930			4.905	-0.51	0.0013	0.0265
	(a) Genbiotic (D) (optho)	1	0.959			0.949	-1.00	0.0017	0.1791
		3	2.877			2.855	-0.76	0.0018	0.0630
		5	4.795			4.770	-0.53	0.0025	0.0524
	(b) Gentamide (D)	1	0.957			0.947	-1.01	0.0026	0.2746
		3	2.871			2.849	-0.78	0.0033	0.1158
		5	4.785			4.759	-0.55	0.0028	0.0588
4	Tobramycin sulphate (pure)	1	0.985	60	64	0.975	-1.06	0.0030	0.3077
		3	2.955			2.932	-0.77	0.0035	0.1194
		5	4.925			4.901	-0.48	0.0027	0.0551
	(a) Tocin (D) (optho)	1	0.955			0.946	-0.90	0.0029	0.3066
		3	2.865			2.844	-0.73	0.0019	0.0668
		5	4.775			4.748	-0.56	0.0016	0.0337

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

(b) Eyebrex (D)	1	0.953			0.944	-0.96	0.0021	0.2225
	3	2.859	60	64	2.837	-0.78	0.0021	0.0740
	5	4.765			4.737	-0.59	0.0015	0.0317
5. Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride (pure)	1	0.983			0.974	-0.94	0.0025	0.2567
	3	2.949	30	10	2.927	-0.75	0.0017	0.0581
	5	4.915			4.887	-0.57	0.0023	0.0471
(a) Cifax (D) (optho)	1	0.951			0.941	-1.01	0.0014	0.1488
	3	2.853	30	10	2.830	-0.79	0.0015	0.0530
	5	4.755			4.727	-0.58	0.0020	0.4230
(b) Citron (D)	1	0.950			0.940	-1.06	0.0019	0.2021
	3	2.850	30	10	2.829	-0.75	0.0015	0.0530
	5	4.750			4.729	-0.45	0.0012	0.0254
6. Norfloxacin (pure)	1	0.982			0.972	-1.02	0.0025	0.2572
	3	2.946	30	10	2.924	-0.75	0.0030	0.1026
	5	4.910			4.885	-0.50	0.0019	0.0389
(a) NorfloX (D) (optho)	1	0.949			0.940	-0.97	0.0031	0.3298
	3	2.847	30	10	2.825	-0.76	0.0026	0.0920
	5	4.745			4.718	-0.57	0.0024	0.0509
7. Tropicamide (pure)	1	0.981			0.971	-1.04	0.0035	0.3605
	3	2.943	30	12	2.919	-0.81	0.0030	0.1028
	5	4.905			4.876	-0.59	0.0022	0.0451
(a) Tropac (D) (optho)	1	0.947			0.938	-0.97	0.0021	0.2239
	3	2.841	30	12	2.819	-0.76	0.0023	0.0816
	5	4.735			4.708	-0.58	0.0020	0.0425
8. Naphazoline hydrochloride (pure)	1	0.975			0.965	-1.04	0.0013	0.1347
	3	2.925	30	3	2.902	-0.77	0.0025	0.0861
	5	4.875			4.850	-0.51	0.0030	0.0619
(a) Zoline (D) (optho)	1	0.945			0.936	-0.93	0.0028	0.2991
	3	2.835	30	3	2.814	-0.75	0.0018	0.0640
	5	4.725			4.699	-0.56	0.0012	0.0255
9. Neomycin sulphate (pure)	1	0.974			0.965	-0.00	0.0022	0.2280
	3	2.922	30	38	2.900	-0.75	0.0017	0.0586
	5	4.870			4.843	-0.55	0.0025	0.0516
(a) Ophodex-N (D) (optho)	1	0.942			0.933	-0.96	0.0025	0.2680
	3	2.826	30	38	2.805	-0.73	0.0017	0.0606
	5	4.710			4.685	-0.54	0.0022	0.0470

D = Drop.

*In each sample nine estimations were done. **Average of nine determinations.

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